

ENHANCING INDEPENDENT ENGLISH LEARNING THROUGH EDTECH AMONG PHARMACY STUDENTS IN MULTILINGUAL SETTINGS

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Relevance. For pharmacy students, English proficiency provides access to global scientific updates, international pharmaceutical literature, and professional communication. In multilingual educational environments, digital technologies (EdTech) that support independent English learning motivate students to study beyond the classroom and accelerate practical language acquisition.

Aim of the study. To determine the effectiveness of EdTech tools in fostering independent English learning among pharmacy students in multilingual settings.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted with 2nd–3rd year pharmacy students of the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute. Participants regularly used online platforms (Quizlet, Kahoot, Duolingo) and interactive video courses. Diagnostic tests and motivation surveys were administered at the beginning and end of the study period to evaluate language progress and learner autonomy. Data were analyzed using descriptive and statistical methods.

Results. Regular use of EdTech tools improved students' vocabulary knowledge by an average of 18–22% and listening comprehension skills by 15% ($p < 0.05$). Survey results also confirmed an increase in motivation for independent English practice.

Conclusions. The integration of digital educational technologies effectively supports independent English learning among pharmacy students. Incorporating EdTech platforms into the regular curriculum significantly enhances students' acquisition of professional English.